

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART III. REDUCTION WITH SODIUM SULPHITE.

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Sulphurous acid and sulphites are reducing agents. Dymond and Hughes (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 71, 314) studied the reducing action of sulphite on acidified potassium permanganate solution. They found that the oxygen used was 90 to 95% of that required for the oxidation of sulphite to sulphate. They accounted for this deficiency as due to the formation of dithionic acid, the potassium salt of which was isolated and analysed. The reaction is represented by the equation :

Alkaline solutions of sulphur dioxide were found by Gilles (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1858, 55, 374), Fordos and Gellis (*J. Pharm. chim.*, 1859, iii, 36, 113) and Buignet (*ibid.*, p. 122) to be almost completely oxidised to sulphate by permanganate; but in acidic solution about one-fifth is oxidised to dithionate.

Hendrixson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 1319, 2156) studied the oxidation of sulphurous acid by dichromate, bromate and iodate in acid solution. The amounts of dichromate and bromate are less than those required by theory for the complete oxidation to sulphate. This discrepancy is regarded as due to the formation of some dithionic acid which resists further oxidation. On the other hand iodate oxidises the sulphite completely to sulphate. The reaction with iodate is represented by the equations :

The oxidation is, therefore, effected by free iodine as in other ordinary iodine oxidations.

Hendrixson (*loc. cit.*) has further shown that sulphite is quantitatively oxidised in acid solution by bromate, dichromate or permanganate on the addition of one-half equivalent of iodide to these oxidants. In the present investigation, sodium sulphite has been used as a reducing agent in acid solution in presence of an excess of potassium iodide to determine iodine, potassium dichromate, potassium ferricyanide, copper sulphate and hydrogen peroxide by the potentiometric method.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

A known weight of sodium sulphite was dissolved in freshly boiled water and the solution kept under hydrogen in a vessel connected with a hydrogen generator and a burette. The strength of the sulphite solution was checked against standard iodine.

A bright platinum foil dipping into a liquid in a titration vessel constituted one-half element; the other was the saturated calomel electrode connected through an agar-agar—KCl bridge. The mixture in the titration vessel was thoroughly stirred and the E.M.F. of the cell was measured on a potentiometric scale after each addition of the titrant.

The estimation of iodine was carried out by directly titrating it against the standard solution of sodium sulphite. In the case of potassium dichromate, potassium ferricyanide and copper sulphate, a known amount of each was mixed with an excess of potassium iodide solution, acidified and the liberated iodine titrated against the standard sodium sulphite. The titrations were conducted in the presence of carbon dioxide to prevent the atmospheric oxidation of hydriodic acid formed in the reactions.

To titrate hydrogen peroxide it was first acidified and then mixed with potassium iodide solution. A few drops of ammonium molybdate were then added to catalyse the reaction.

A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. One titration for each substance, as typical of that set, is recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Titration of 25 c.c. of *N*/20 iodine (0.1586 g.) against sodium sulphite (*N*/10.08).

Sodium sulphite.	E.M.F. (volts).	<i>E</i> / <i>C</i> (m.volts/c.c.).	Sodium sulphite.	E.M.F. (volts).	<i>E</i> / <i>C</i> (m.volts/c.c.).
11.50 c.c.	0.208		12.60	0.079	
		16			140
12.00	0.200		12.65	0.072	
		27			70
12.30	0.192		12.75	0.065	
		40			47
12.40	0.188		12.90	0.058	
		50			33
12.50	0.183		13.20	0.048	
		140			18
12.55	0.176		13.70	0.039	
		1940			

TABLE II.

Titration of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (0.0613 g.) mixed with 50 c.c. of KI (N/10) and 30 c.c. of H_2SO_4 (10N) against sodium sulphite (N/11.40).

Sodium sulphite.	E.M.F. (volts).	E/C (m.volts/c.c.).	Sodium sulphite.	E.M.F. (volts).	E/C (m.volts/c.c.).
13.00 c.c.	0.171	16	14.20	0.143	<u>1660</u>
13.50	0.163	20	14.25	0.060	120
13.90	0.155	25	14.30	0.054	80
14.10	0.150	40	14.40	0.046	50
14.15	0.148	100	14.60	0.036	30
			15.20	0.021	

TABLE III.

Titration of potassium ferricyanide (0.4109 g.) mixed with 25 c.c. of KI (2N) and 25 c.c. of HCl (5N) against sodium sulphite (N/9.72).

Sodium sulphite.	E.M.F. (volts).	E/C (m.volts/c.c.).	Sodium sulphite.	E.M.F. (volts).	E/C (m.volts/c.c.).
11.00 c.c.	0.176	14	12.10	0.151	<u>1640</u>
11.50	0.169	20	12.15	0.069	120
11.70	0.165	25	12.20	0.063	60
11.90	0.160	30	12.30	0.057	35
12.00	0.157	40	12.50	0.050	28
12.05	0.155	80	13.00	0.036	16
			13.50	0.028	

TABLE IV.

Titration of $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ (0.2050 g.) mixed with 25 c.c. of KI (2 N) and 5 c.c. of H_2SO_4 (N) against sodium sulphite (N/11.36).

Sodium sulphite.	E. M. F. (volts).	E/C (m.volts/c.c.).	Sodium sulphite.	E. M. F. (volts).	E/C (m.volts/c.c.).
7.90 c.c.	0.204	16	9.35	0.072	80
8.40	0.196	24	9.40	0.068	60
8.90	0.184	35	9.45	0.065	50
9.10	0.177	50	9.55	0.060	25
9.20	0.172	60	9.75	0.055	18
9.25	0.169	60	10.25	0.046	12
9.30	0.166	1880	10.75	0.040	

TABLE V.

Titration of H_2O_2 (25 c.c., 0.0275 *N*—0.0117 g.) mixed with 10 c.c. of H_2SO_4 (*N*) and 13 c.c. of KI (*N*) against sodium sulphite (*N*/9.60).

Sodium sulphite.	E. M. F. (volts).	<i>E/C</i> (m.volts/c.c.).	Sodium sulphite.	E. M. F. (volts).	<i>E/C</i> (m.volts/c.c.).
5.00 c.c.	0.247	6			
5.50	0.244	10			180
6.00	0.239	20	6.65	0.063	60
6.20	0.235	40	6.70	0.060	50
6.40	0.227	80	6.80	0.055	27
6.50	0.219	160	7.10	0.047	16
6.55	0.211	2780	7.60	0.039	11
6.60	0.072		8.60	0.028	

The curves for the above titrations are given in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1.

Curves 1—5 refer respectively to $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, I_2 , $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, CuSO_4 , $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and H_2O_2 .

DISCUSSION.

With the addition of standard sodium sulphite solution, the E.M.F. decreased steadily till the equivalence point. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential in each case. For the addition of 0.05 c.c. of titrant, the inflection potential was of the order of 97, 83, 82,

94 and 139 millivolts for iodine, potassium dichromate, potassium ferricyanide, copper sulphate, and hydrogen peroxide respectively. After the equivalence point, there was again a fall in the potential which became steady on further addition of the reagent.

From the volume of the sodium sulphite solution required in each titration corresponding to the equivalence point, the amount of the substance was calculated. The values obtained are compared with the amounts of the substance taken as shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Iodine		Potassium dichromate		Potassium ferricyanide	
Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
0.1586 g.	0.1584 g.	0.0613 g.	0.0612 g.	0.4109 g.	0.4108 g.
0.1921	0.1920	0.0971	0.0971	0.6322	0.6320
0.2230	0.2231	0.1245	0.1245	0.9271	0.9271
0.2514	0.2512	0.1688	0.1689	1.1244	1.1242
Copper sulphate		Hydrogen peroxide			
Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
0.2050 g.	0.2051 g.	0.0117 g.	0.0116 g.		
0.4382	0.4382	0.0328	0.0325		
0.6917	0.6918	0.0574	0.0571		
0.8543	0.8542	0.0765	0.0764		

These results show that iodine, potassium dichromate, potassium ferricyanide, copper sulphate and hydrogen peroxide can be determined quantitatively by the potentiometric method.

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